

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GILBERT, III****FIRST NAME: JAMES****PROGRAM CODE: MSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 01****INSTRUCTOR: Professor Kabiru Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MS Word 2019, OS MS Windows 10

ACA-401 PERIOD 1, RP # 1

1) INTRODUCTION

The first essay for ACA-401 requires a response to the ACA-401 Coursepack Period 01, later referred to simply as “Coursepack.” The Coursepack provides an introductory overview covering: (1) essay writing basics; (2) general rules for writing; (3) a summary guide to grammar and style guides; (4) differences between American and British English; as well as (5) a Chicago-Turabian crib sheet.

I will be commenting on Sections 1 and 2, with particular emphasis on plagiarism. As for Section 3, while useful, I do not have reason to comment. Regarding Sections 4 and 5, I do not have any comments. Not having written an academic paper in approximately 15-years, I did find the Coursepack useful and worthwhile. And thankfully, from where I now sit, there is nowhere to go but forward.

Well, it feels like all of those years past when I found myself procrastinating or starting way too late to begin researching/writing a paper. I am, right now, determined to get through this paper. And then moving forward, follow one of writing’s ‘golden rules’: “Start writing early - the earlier, the better. Starting (early) cuts down on anxiety, beats procrastination (one paper writing problem I hope/need to drop ASAP), and gives you time to develop ideas” (EUCLID 2015, 3).

2) WRITING STRUCTURE

One of the things that I find interesting is the suggestion to “write the introduction and conclusion after the body” (Ibid). I have not done it this way, and I am not comfortable doing so as of this time. It makes sense to me to wait until the end of the process before

writing the conclusion. After all, the writing process should be fluid. Ideas, sources, changes of thought/direction all give reason to leave the conclusion to the end. But not writing the introduction until having written the body of work does not make sense to me.

While writing a body of work is an ever-changing process, it also requires a solid premise. Starting with a strong premise allows the writing to materialize and manifest into the desired result. A reason as to what the work will represent. Why is it important? Or at least why it should interest and entice the reader. One might argue that is the point of a detailed outline. But what is one outlining without a solid premise? Should not the premise form the foundation for the introduction? Page three of the Coursepack seems to also back this approach: “4. Writing the essay, structure, introduction: Open with a short orientation (introduce the topic area(s) with a general, broad opening sentence (or two); answer the question with a thesis statement; and provide a summary or ‘road map’ of your essay (keep it brief, but mention all the main ideas)” (Ibid). Similarly, on page four, under Questions to ask yourself, it also lends to the argument of writing a solid introduction at the start. I find the two directions confusing (Ibid).

3) PLAGIARISM

I will now discuss plagiarism. The Coursepack defines plagiarism as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2015, 31). Committing plagiarism is essentially the *worst* offense a writer can make. Expulsion from school, professional disgrace, intellectual theft; these are grave consequences. And when confronted with a charge of plagiarism, ignorance is not an accepted defense. Plagiarism will continue in academia until the world comes to understand, accept, and respect the legal rights of intellectual property holders.

In my opinion, the Coursepack provides ample justification for using block quotes such as the one below (EUCLID 2015, 21).

Educators have long recognized that international trainees, especially from developing nations, have particular trouble with US standards of scholarly writing and are at significantly higher risk for committing plagiarism than their US peers [4–8]... A host of factors may make international trainees susceptible to committing plagiarism. Among the most important are: the normalcy of plagiarism in many environments internationally; the lack of formal misconduct policies in many countries and operationally vague policies on plagiarism where they do exist; philosophical arguments against US notions of originality, intellectual property, and authority; and non-native speakers’ difficulties in writing in English (Heitman and Litewka 2011, 104-108).

Now, with the above said in mind, it was what was not said in the Coursepack that caught my attention. And with all honesty, I come out on both sides of the argument that follows. In my opinion, the issue not addressed is one of great importance. I think this issue should be brought to the student’s attention from the outset of the program. So they might better understand the implications and consequences of such conduct. Because these are by no means crystal clear. The issue to which I am referring is ‘self-plagiarism.’ Right

off the bat, I call foul. After all, not in theory, but reality, **you own the copyright** to work(s) from which you are borrowing. You made an effort, did the research, created the work(s). Your name is at the top of the paper(s). You own it. At face-value, *self-plagiarism* sounds to me like an oxymoron. Well, like so many things, it is a bit more complicated.

Self-plagiarism, by definition, is essentially the same as plagiarism but with one glaring difference. The writer is reusing a portion of their work that was already submitted. It is a slippery slope one does not want to be on, and for a good reason. Works submitted to, or paid for by magazines, newspapers, publishing houses, etc., expect that they will receive what they paid for: a quality, well-written, original pieces of authorship.

One famous example of self-plagiarism is that of journalist Jonah Lehrer. Lehrer contributed works to *The Guardian*, *The New York Times Magazine*, *The New Yorker*, *The Wall Street Journal*, and *Wired Magazine*, among others. It turned out that Lehrer was a prolific self-plagiarizer. And in the world of journalism, self-plagiarism constitutes an extremely serious offense. Another example is that of well-known contributor Fareed Zakaria. Zakaria was suspended from both *CNN* and *Newsweek* for multiple cases of plagiarism and self-plagiarism.

With this in mind, it is easy to see both sides of the issue. But the waters are muddied even further when an organization does not view self-plagiarism as the same pariah as the world of journalism or academia. What happens when one contributes work to an entity that does not similarly see self-plagiarism? According to the United States Department of Health and Human Services, “Self-plagiarism is NOT considered research misconduct in accordance to 42 CFR 93” (Miguel Roig 2015).

4) CONCLUSION

Throughout one’s degree program, there presents a considerable chance of knowledge and subject matter overlap from essay to essay. And as we have seen, there is not a universal standard for acceptance/nonacceptance of self-plagiarism across disciplines, geography, or institutions. This creates a somewhat perilous environment for the author, who might honestly not be aware of this issue. While I find it strange to cite one’s work, I now have a real awareness of this potentially dangerous pitfall. And I am sure that while I am dreading having to write another four or five response papers on writing/grammar basics and essentials, I now accept that there is a reason for this madness.

REFERENCES

EUCLID University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf>. (last accessed February 5, 2020).

Elizabeth Heitman and Sergio Litewka. 2011. International Perspectives on Plagiarism and Considerations for Teaching International Trainees. *Journal of Urologic Oncology*. 29 (1), 104-108. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3038591/> (last accessed February 5, 2020).

Miguel Roig, Ph.D. *Avoiding Plagiarism, Self-Plagiarism, and Other Questionable Writing Practices: A Guide to Ethical Writing*. Department of Health and Human Services, Office of Research Integrity 2003, revised in 2006 and 2015. <https://ori.hhs.gov/avoiding-plagiarism-self-plagiarism-and-other-questionable-writing-practices-guide-ethical-writing> (last accessed February 5, 2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.